

Evaluation of the impact of Conflict Management on Managerial Performance: A Case study of the National Ministry of Finance and Planning, Juba, South Sudan

Chol Gabriel Majer

Abstract:

The study's overall goal is to assess the influence of conflict management on managerial performance at the Ministry of Finance and Planning, and it employs a descriptive research methodology. The study employed a sample size of 44 respondents, which included senior managers, line managers, and support workers. The respondents were selected using a simple random sampling method and purposive sampling. In this study, questionnaires were employed as the primary data gathering tool. The data gathered in the field was analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 16.0, which included descriptive statistics like percentages as well as inferential statistics like frequencies percentages analyses. According to the findings of this study, the majority of respondents believe that dialogue influences conflict management and managerial performance. They also believe that involving employees in conflict resolution leads to the achievement of a mutually optimal solution, implying that using an integrating strategy to manage conflicts improves managerial performance. The study concludes that conflict management strategies and managerial performance are linked, and that the most commonly used strategies are integrating, avoiding, and obliging. It is recommended that the Ministry of Finance and Planning highlight and use at least two or one strategy to ensure objectivity.

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About Author (s)

Chol Gabriel Majer, MBA (Generic) & PGDBA, University of Juba, South Sudan.

1. Introduction

Workplace disputes abound across the world, fueled by differences in religion, culture, personality, and competing interests in political power, economics, social standing, and prestige. Human people frequently argue over a variety of topics in many aspects of their life. This circumstance develops when there is a lack of agreement or consensus on a specific issue, or when one party infringes on another's private rights. The arts and popular cultural scene serve as a vehicle for promoting peace, social tolerance, and cohesiveness. The world in which we live is not without strife. Arts and popular culture provide a creative avenue through which various conflicts can be resolved in the work place. Researchers say properly managed conflict promotes open communication, collaborative decision making, regular feedback, and timely resolution of conflict. Open communication and collaboration enhance the flow of new ideas and strengthen work relationships, which can have a positive effect on employee morale. Regular feedback and timely resolution of conflict has the potential of improving employee satisfaction and job performance. A negative working environment that does not promote conflict resolution can result in poor employee behavior and job performance. Unmanaged conflict promotes dysfunctional communication and poor behavior among staff. Poor behavior on the part of one employee has the power to affect overall employee morale, which results in lower productivity. According to Dana (2000), conflict is not just an annoyance. Individuals do not have the communication or interpersonal skills to resolve their disputes. The conflict can grow and spread to others, eventually affecting their job performance, which, in turn, affects the job satisfaction of others, as well. In addition to the staff not having the communication skills to address their disputes, their leaders Once human resources personnel are involved, the process becomes punitive and results in disciplinary action, which contributes to an even greater reduction in employee morale and employee satisfaction. Within any institution, there are usually different positions and jobs. People occupying these positions have different perceptions, goals, thoughts and concerns. It is difficult to conceptualize society or an organization without inherent differences and contradictions and these lead to conflict. In organizations, a serious problem can be conflicts that are very serious. This is bad practice that will make it impossible for the workers to go to the same place for work. Conflict is a natural and inevitable part of people working together and should be kept at a manageable level where it will not disorganize the activities of the institution towards the attainment of its objectives. Conflict management may also be beneficial to the institution where it brings about radical change in the institutional power structure, current interaction pattern and entrenched attitude and also can lead to an increase in productivity. While some conflicts are functional, others are not. It can also affect the organization negatively when it is associated with decreased employee satisfaction, insubordination, decreased productivity, leads to economic loss, fragmentation, to mention but a few. It is the management's major responsibility to devise strategies for bringing down conflict as low as possible, which will enable the institution to still function to succeed. Against this background, the study is being carried out on the negative effect of conflict.

Integrated conflict management and managerial performance methods have been developed in Sub-Saharan African nations such as Burundi, Central African Republic, Cote d'Ivoire, Democratic Republic of Congo, Guinea, Liberia, Mali, Sierra Leone, and Sudan. This program aims to assist African countries that have been afflicted by violence (CASA). In South Sudan; there are regular border disputes and conflicts in the government, as well as inter-personal problems in nearly all institutions. These battles have stifled growth and managerial effectiveness, resulting in low productivity and a weak economy. The necessity to enhance management performance has become more prominent as time has gone on.

In order to achieve performance, there is a need to align the organizational objectives with the employees' agreed measures, skills, competency requirements, development plans and the delivery of results. Although performance has been traditionally conceptualized in terms of financial measures, some scholars have proposed broader managerial performance. In fact, some types of conflict encourage new solutions to problems and enhance the creativity in the organization. In these cases, managers will want to encourage the conflict. Therefore, managers should stimulate functional conflict and prevent or resolve dysfunctional conflict. The consequences of conflict can be positive or negative. Conflict management among employees in an institution is not simply inevitable; rather it is the nature of complex institutions. However, if managed properly, it can have a positive impact on employee satisfaction and performance. Research indicates that management executives are spending twice as much time settling employees' disputes than they did a decade ago. If conflicts are managed properly by applying the best course of action, the organization can increase its performance in terms of utilizing the scarce resources and achieving the organizational objectives. Conversely, unmanaged conflict negatively impacts both employee satisfaction and performance. Timely management of conflict has the potential of improving employee satisfaction and job performance. It is important to note that managers have at their disposal a variety of conflict management styles: avoiding, accommodating, competing, compromising, and collaborating. One way of classifying styles of conflict management is to examine the styles. Generally, the purpose of research is to evaluate the impact of conflict management on managerial performance and objectives. This research studied the evaluation of conflict management on managerial performance by using employees of the Ministry of Finance and Planning MOFP in Juba. The significance of this study lies in the fact that its finding will enable managers or directors in the institution of the case study to have in depth knowledge of work place conflict and how to manage conflict in the institution of the case study not only in South Sudan but across Africa. The aim of this research is to evaluate the impact of conflict management on managerial performance, a case study of the National Ministry of Finance and planning South Sudan.

Previous research worldwide has found that workplace conflicts have negative impacts on conflict management and managerial performance. However, research has shown that today's workplace conflict may take the form of personality conflicts between employees, between an employee and supervisor, or between an employee and the institution when the employee disagrees with a change in mission or policy that comes from faceless executives. In the Ministry of Finance and planning, there are many workers who operate in ever changing work environments. These environments have potential sources of conflicts. This has been evidenced in the increasing employee turnover arising out of conflicts, particularly in role play, unclear duties and responsibilities hence decline in employee performance. Ministry of Finance and planning; Headquarter Juba. However, it is not clear whether workplace conflicts are destructive enough to cause a decline in the performance of employees. Such a situation is worth investigating. Therefore, this investigated whether workplace conflicts have in anyway affected employee performance in Juba. The full day work has created grievances on the part of staff, especially staff who had a big working load compared to others. There seems to be an unfair assignment and other managers at various levels. The competitive market situations also negatively contribute to the dissatisfaction of individual teachers, especially the young ones, and if permission was not granted to them for further education, it created tension in schools. The incompetency of some managers to understand the professional problems of employees and their inability to handle and solve the problems; improper communication between the staff and top management has been influencing regular conflict in some schools. Conflicts in the institution of case study, in selected secondary schools, are seen as destructive

and affect activities. There is a need to identify types of conflict prevailing; investigate factors that initiate conflict between employees and other stakeholders, and examine what strategies are employed to handle conflict in an institution. Finally, an attempt is made to identify the best strategies to be used in managing conflicts in the institution of case study.

The Objectives of the Study are (i) To determine the level of conflict management in terms of task, procedural and interpersonal conflict in the Ministry of Finance and Planning, (ii) To determine the effect of workplace conflict management on managerial performance in the establishment. (iii) To examine whether collective bargaining conflict management strategy positively affects employees in terms of motivation, job satisfaction and commitment to work, and (iv) To examine the extent to which budgeting competence affects managerial performance.

The Ministry of Finance and Planning is responsible for maintaining control over public spending, setting the direction of the South Sudan's fiscal policy, and is working to achieve strong, equitable and sustainable economic growth. It "manages the overall revenue, expenditure, and financing of the Government of the Republic of South Sudan's and provides the Government with advice on the broad financial affairs of South Sudan's a in support of the Government's economic and social objectives."Its duties include "preparing the Central Government budget; developing tax policy and legislation; managing Government borrowings on financial markets; determining expenditure allocations to different Government institutions; transferring central grants to local governments; developing regulatory policy for the country's financial sector in cooperation with the Ministry Finance and Planning of South Sudan's and representing South Sudan within international financial institution.

2. Literature review

Disagreement, disagreements, and conflicting interests, wants, and wishes between two or more persons are all signs of conflict (Hellriegel& Slocum, 1996). Conflict management is a concept and a set of skills that help people and communities better understand and deal with conflict in all parts of their life. Conflict has never been a desirable or bad idea, but rather a necessary and result-oriented element of existence (Ghaffar, 2005). According to Owens (1998), good workplace conflict management, such as seeing it as a problem to be solved and stressing the collaborative nature of institutional activity may result in outcomes that are both productive and beneficial to the institutions' health. Ineffective conflict management, on the other hand, can lead to a climate that exacerbates the situation and likely developed a downward spiral of mounting frustration, deteriorating insanity, and harsh practices in the name of administering the negotiated contract and emphasizing the adversarial relationship between employees and management.

2.1 Conflict Management

Conflict management involves implementing strategies to decrease the negative aspect of conflict and increasing the positive at a level equal to or higher than where a conflict is taking place. Conflict management is the practice of being able to identify and handle conflict in a sensible, fair and efficient manner. It is important that there are people who understand conflict and know how to resolve them because conflict a business is a natural part of the workplace. (Cook and Philip; 2001)

2.2 Meaning of Institution Conflict

Conflict is conceived to be an outcome of behavior which is an integral part of human life. Dunlop (2002) expresses that conflict is a disagreement between two or more individuals or

groups with each individual or group trying to make the other accept its view or position. Ugbaja (2002) defines institutional conflict as any dispute, individual or group, that arises in the work place which causes disharmony among a group of workers or between an individual and the management. Sinclair (2005) sees conflict as a disagreement between employees and their employers.

2.3. Types of conflicts in Public Institutions

2.3.1. Constructive Conflict

Constructive conflict, otherwise known as constructive controversy, is defined as situations when one person's ideas, information, conclusions, theories, and opinions are incompatible with those of another, and the two seek to reach an agreement (Johnson, & Tjosvold, 2006). Constructive conflict can lead to, easier transitions in change, increased effectiveness, better communication, increased involvement, increased productivity, and improved problem solving quality (Haas, 1999; Lippit, 1982; Tjosvold, 2006)

2.3.2. Destructive Conflict

Destructive conflict is defined as a social situation in which there are perceived incompatibilities in goals or values between two or more parties, attempts by the parties to control one another, and antagonistic feelings toward each other (Fischer, 2006). Destructive conflict has been found to lead to uncivil behaviors in the workplace. Consequently, an increase in workplace incivility negatively influences workers' health, attitudes, and performance (Fischer, 2006; Rahim, 2001) despite these categories, conflict is an inevitable part of organizational life since the goals of different stakeholders such as managers and staffs are often incompatible. Conflict arises in groups because of the scarcity of freedom, position, and resources. People who value independence tend to resist the need for interdependence and, to some extent, conformity within a group. People who seek power therefore struggle with others for position or status within the group. Pondy (1967) identified three types of conflict in organizations; bargaining conflict, bureaucratic conflict, and systems conflict. Galabawa (2000) also identified the types of conflict; these are procedural conflict, cognitive conflict, affective conflict and goal conflict.

2.3.3. Procedural Conflict

It is very common that in institution the management and the employees may differ in the methods, ways and means of making decision or solving problems. These differences amounts to procedural conflict, it means that in all cases, where the employees or other people differ over the process of resolving matters as procedural conflict occur. The most common procedural conflict occurs in negotiations between trade unions and management. The conflict resulted in several industrial actions leading to disruptions of the day to day activities

2.3.4. Cognitive Conflict

Cognitive conflict, which is a common form of conflict among individuals, occurs when there is an incompatibility of ideas and thoughts within one individual or individuals. In some cases, it is referred to as an individual conflict. It is often occurs when an individual has two different ideas on solving a problem, where upon it becomes difficult to decide on which idea to adopt. In this case, if the situation prolongs, a cognitive conflict occurs (Galabawa, 2000)

2.3.5. Affective Conflict

When institutions experience differences of feeling and emotions are incompatible within an individual or between individuals, affective conflict occurs. Although it is difficult to openly experience differences of feeling and emotions between individuals, it is very common the two individuals may have different feelings about the same situation. For example two employees could experience different feelings when discussing issues of their section. One

could experience positive feelings about the decision and another could threaten. This would certainly result in affective conflict between these two employees (Galabawa, 2000)

2.3.6. Goal Conflict

Goal conflict usually occurs when for example, the subordinates view on the productivity standards or performance indicators become incompatible or totally contrary to the views of their supervisors. In this case a goal conflict occurs because the subordinate and the superior do not agree on what should be achieved (Galabawa, 2000)

2.3.7. Scarce Resource Conflict

Babyegeya (2000) classifies conflict according to resources. A scarce resource conflict is the conflict which takes place when there are insufficient resources in an institution. This happens when some members in certain departments start complaining that other departments are favored in resource distribution while others are disfavored or ignored.

2.3.8. Interdependence Conflict

Interdependence conflict is the type of conflict which flow out from work relationship and the need to work together. During the execution of functions the groups may use different strategies in accomplishing the work. Or one group may not see to cooperate with another group because of perceiving themselves as being more important than others. This can cause clashes or reduced cooperation between the groups leading to poor performance. (Babyegeya, 2002)

2.3.9. Intra-Group Conflict

Groups, be they are formal or informal, have their own norms and standards of behavior that members are expected to adhere to. Individuals and groups come into conflicts when members do not abide by the groups' rule (Rahim, 1986). There are several causes of such conflict: leadership style, group composition and size, cohesiveness and group-think, external threats and their outcomes.

2.3.10. Inter-Group Conflict

This kind of conflict refers to the disagreement or differences between two or more units or groups (departments) in an organization. Such conflict is generated from differentiation of tasks, differences in "culture" across groups (departments), need for joint decision making, dependence on shared resources, communication difficulties, ethnic or racial backgrounds (Hellriegel and Slocum, 1982). On the other hand, Jehn and Mannix (2001) proposed three types of conflict in workgroups in general: relationship, task and process conflict

2.3.11. Constructive Conflict

The integrationist view does not propose that all conflicts are good. Rather, some conflicts support the goals of the group and improve its performance; these are functional, constructive forms of conflict. Robbin (2001) defines functional conflict as the conflict that supports the goals of the group and improves its organizational performance. The argument is that if conflict leads to normal competition among groups and the groups work harder and produce more, it is advantageous to the group and the institution. It is viewed as a confrontation between two ideas, goals and parties that improves employees and organizational performance one of the main benefits of constructive conflict is that it gives its members a chance to identify the problems and see the opportunities. Also, it can inspire to new ideas, learning, and growth among individuals (Kinicki and Kreitner, 2008)

2.3.12. Destructive Conflict

There are conflicts that hinder group performance; these are dysfunctional or destructive forms of conflict. Conflict is inevitable and desirable in the institutions, but when not effectively handled, conflict can tear relationships apart and, thus, interfere with the exchange of ideas, information and resources in groups and between departments. Dysfunctional conflict hinders and prevents organizational goals from being achieved

Dysfunctional conflict usually hinders managerial performance and leads to decreased productivity. This conflict orientation is characterized by competing individual interests overriding the overall interest of the business. Managers withhold information from one another. Employees sabotage others' work, either intentionally or through subtle, conflict-motivated disinterest in team work (Kinicki and Kreitner, 2008)

2.4. Conceptual Framework

Conceptual frame work is used in research to outline possible causes of action or to present preferred approach to an idea or thought. The researcher of this study developed a model to guide the presentation of the theoretical ideas in which this study is laying upon the explanation of the phenomenon. The model is illustrated and diagrammatically presented as follows; Conceptual framework of the study encompasses independent and dependent variables related to the five research questions.

In this model, the independent variables were the types of conflict (goal conflict, scarce of resource conflict, authority conflict, and procedural conflict) and causes of conflict (scarce of resource, different in attitudes, poor communication) which were taken into consideration during data analysis as explanatory variables of the study. The dependent variables of managerial Performance this study were styles of conflict management (Accountability Efficiency, Effectiveness, Quality, Comprehensiveness, and Transparency).The dependent variables (managerial Performance) depend on independent variables that is, types and causes of conflict. This implies that the success of conflict management styles is determined much by the type and causes of conflict and there is no particular style of managerial performance that can be used to handle every conflict

Conflict Management

- Avoidance
- Accommodation
- Competition
- Compromise
- Collaborations
- Integrating

Managerial Performance

- Accountability
- Efficiency
- Effectiveness
- Quality
- Comprehensiveness
- Transparency

3. Methodology

This chapter will focus on research methodology sampling area, research design, study sample and sampling strategies. The area of study, focus of the study, population, sample size and sampling techniques, population, sample size, sampling techniques, simple random sampling, sample selection, methods of data collection, instrument, questionnaire, interviews, data analysis plan, data collection procedure, data analysis and interpretation, documentary review checklist, quality control, validity, instrument validity, procedure of data collection, data collection methods and techniques, data analysis, quantitative data analysis, qualitative data analysis, measurement of variables, reliability analysis, ethical considerations and chapter summary that will be used to achieve the objective of the study. The information will be computerized and processed using SPSS computer software. Tables and graphs (Bar graphs) were highly employed, narrative notes were used to explain the information

summarized in tables and percentages. The data will be then coded and fed into a computer program (The Statistical Package SPSS) for easy analysis and interpretation of results. Primary data will be analyzed through descriptive statistics, Frequency analysis will be used to analyze the primary data using the SPSS software

4. Data presentation, Analysis and Interpretation

4.1. Data Analysis Methods

After the fieldwork before analysis, all the questionnaires were adequately checked for completeness. The information was coded and entered into a spread sheet and analyzed using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences). The data was checked to ensure that the output was free from outliers and the effect of missing responses was at the minimum. Quantitative analysis involved generating descriptive statistics. The descriptive statistics included frequency tallies, and their corresponding percentage scores. The findings were presented by using tables and charts as found appropriate. Qualitative analysis involved categorizing of data from interviews and field notes into common themes and presented using frequency distribution tables and charts. Analysis and Discussion of Data in analyzing the data, the study revealed that inter-personal conflict prevailed within the institution which is conflict management between two or more individuals who do not share the same goals or values or who are in opposition to one another. And the second most answered is inter-personal which is conflict within the person, this arises when the individual due to actual or perceived pressures from incompatible goal expect action

4.2. Demographic characteristics of respondents

The study required the respondents to indicate their demographic characteristics among which included; age, gender, marital status, highest level of education and number of years serving the institution. These were examined as they were presumed to influence work place conflicts management and managerial performance of employees.

4.2.1. Age and Sex of the Respondents

The researcher found that age and sex are important demographic variables in this study because they enable the researcher to find out whether employment was influenced by age and sex.

4.1. Response Rate

Forty four (100%) out of Forty four respondents took part in the research. The questionnaires were delivered by hand to those in the Ministry of Finance and Planning Juba

4.1. Gender of Respondents

Sex roles have an important component in determining the behavior or reaction of respondents towards conflicts in an organization. It is therefore significant to examine genders a category in this study. The data below show the Gender of the Respondents

Table.4.1. Distribution of employee by gender

Gender	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Female	14	31.8	31.8
Male	30	68.2	100.0
Total	44	100.0	

Data Source: Researcher field Survey, 2020

Out of the 44 employees, 68.2% were male while the remaining 31.8% were female. There is gender balance among employees in the institution. The policy of gender equity has been upheld in the institution

Data Source: Researcher field Survey, 2020

From the diagram above it can be revealed that 68% of the male staff responded to the various questions probably because of the nature of conflict in the office. This is closely followed by 32% were female respectively; these sections have also encountered conflict in their various departments. Hence, the administration, male higher percentage of the number than female of the institution from the above analysis

4.2. Analysis and Discursion of age group of Respondents

Table 4.2. Analysis and Discursion of age group of Respondents

Age	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
56 Years and above	2	4.5	4.5
46-55 Years	4	9.1	13.6
less than 6 Years	6	13.6	27.3
36-45 Years	14	31.8	59.1
26-35 Years	18	40.9	100.0
Total	44	100.0	

Data Source: Researcher field Survey, 2020

On the basis of age as shown in table 4.2, all respondents were above 35 years with over 60% of them aging above 50 years. Although, age may not always reflect knowledge, the caliber of respondents was observed to have adequately gathered so much knowledge and experience over their life time. This indicates that majority of the respondents are not on retirement age that shows the organization have strong men and women to work in the institution for a longer period of time. However, the ministry has to employ more youth into the system to replace the retired staff in the near future.

4.3. Educational Background of the Respondent

Education levels vary substantially among people in a workplace. A higher level of education can be expected to increase in organization, as educated people are more likely tube engaged in various sections in the judiciary. In this study the educational levels of the respondents is significant because it is likely to impact on how conflict can be resolved when it happened in the workplace. The table below shows the Educational Background of the Respondents

Table .4.3. Educational Background of the Respondent

Qualifications	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Certificate	5	11.4	11.4
Masters" Degree	8	18.2	29.5
Diploma	15	34.1	63.6
Undergraduate Degree	16	36.4	100.0
Total	44	100.0	

Data Source: Researcher field Survey, 2020

Table 4.3: Educational qualification of the participants the study findings revealed that 36.4% of the participants were Undergraduate Degree holders as their highest educational qualification and Diploma holders with 34.1% Masters" Degree 18.2%, Certificate 11.4% were holders of undergraduate degrees were majority. It can be deduced from the study that employees were educated hence were in a position to understand the role of interpersonal communication in managing peer co-worker conflict. It is evident that, education level has an influence on the job satisfaction and employee performance. When employee has improved their education levels they become more aware of the job responsibilities as well as, their rights at work. Respondent insists that, conflict can occur to higher educated employees in the institution because; they know and understand their rights when management misuses their power. The findings concur with that who argues that, the worker who had high education level are stronger in fighting their rights compared to those who had moderate or low level of education. They conclude that education in the institutional has influence on conflict management occurrences for better managerial Performance

Figure 1: 4.Educational Background of the Respondents

4.4. Analysis of Marital Status of Employees

Marital status is another bio data that was asserted to be influencing dysfunctional conflict at the workplace. The results of employees' rating are indicated in table 4.4.

Table 4. Marital Status of respondents

Marital Status	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Divorced	4	9.1	9.1
Single	6	13.6	22.7
Married	34	77.3	100.0
Total	44	100.0	

Data Source: Researcher field Survey, 2020

From Table 4.4, Majority Married 34 (77.3%) of the respondents marital Status to fill vacant positions in the institution. Howe Marital Status, this observation is contrary to a study that indicates that the most Marital Status. Other Single 13.6% and divorced 9.1% respondents respectively. This implies that the institution has more married employees than unmarried one. When the corporation faces dysfunctional conflict it means that, married couples were more engaged in the dysfunctional conflict. This is likely to bring marital conflict into workplace and lastly affect the performance of the work. Indicates in his findings that, marital status, demographic groups differ among married and unmarried. He argued that if the conflict happened at the institution may be influenced mostly by married employees

4.5. Job Title of Respondents

Table 5. Job Title of Respondents

Job title	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Directors	4	9.1	9.1
Budget Staff	6	13.6	22.7
Administrators	10	22.7	45.5
Accountants	24	54.5	100.0
Total	44	100.0	

Data Source: Researcher field Survey, 2020

Table 5 depicts that teachers constituted the largest number of respondents that is 24 Accountants (54.5%) of the respondents. Administrators were 10 (22.7%), and 13.6% officers were 9.1%. head of Department. The findings concluded that, Job title of respondents in institution has significance influence on conflict if those employees not satisfied with their

job. The studies concluded that occupation of core function has positive impact on conflict management and managerial performance.

4.6. Working experience of employees

Work output and productivity largely depends on appropriate experience. It was therefore necessary to establish the experience of the employees. Table 6 below indicate their responses

4.6. Duration of Respondents Working In the Ministry

The period of years a person has-been in the ministry may determine the number of time she/she has encounter conflict in the work place and have idea of what causes the conflict and the kind of effects it sometimes have on the productivity of the employees. The table below is the distribution of data on the duration of respondents.

Table. 6. Duration of Respondents Working In the Ministry

Duration of Service	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
17 Years and above	2	4.5	4.5
11-16 Years	12	27.3	31.8
5-10 Years	14	31.8	63.6
Less than 5 years	16	36.4	100.0
Total	44	100.0	

Data Source: Researcher field Survey, 2020

In Table 7, 36.4% of the employees had a working experience of less than five year, another 31.8% had working experience of between 5 and 10 years, 27.3% had worked for between 11 and 16 years while 4.5% had a working experience of over 17 years, the majority were middle staff members of institution.

4.7. Common Types of Conflict exist in an institution

Table 4.7. Common Types of Conflict exist in an institution

Options	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Goal	6	13.6	13.6
Procedural conflict	8	18.2	31.8
Scare resources conflict	13	29.5	61.4
Authority	17	38.6	100.0
Total	44	100.0	

Data Source: Researcher field Survey, 2020

Table 4.7 Types of conflicts occurring in the institution Goal 13.6% Procedural conflict 18.2% Scare resources conflict 29.5% Authority 38.6% the respondents indicate others type of conflict that occurs in the institution is interpersonal intra-personal conflict and personal-group conflict respectively. Inter-group conflict whiles "All of the above." conflict occurs within an employee when they fail to meet his goal because of personal inability or short comings. Interpersonal conflict occurs between employees as a result of clash of personal interests. Person-group conflict occurs between an individual employee and co-workers as result of such things as favoritism, discrimination and segregation. Inter-group conflict occurs between different groups or trade unions in an organization. All these types of conflict regularly occur in our organizations.

4.2. Conflict between top Management and Staff

Table.4.2. Conflict between top Management and Staff

Options	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Availability for training	8	18.2	18.2
Poor implementation of project/activities	16	36.4	54.5
Opportunity for promotion	20	45.5	100.0
Total	44	100.0	

Data Source: Researcher field Survey, 2020

The result of analysis indicated the availability for training 18.2% Poor implementation of project/activities 36.4% Opportunity for promotion 45.5%.The study sought to explore the Conflict between top Management Staff amongst co-workers at institution of study. The findings are discussed in detail above

4.3. Major style use to solve Conflict institutions in and institution

Table.4.3. Major Style use to solve Conflict institutions in and institution

Options	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Avoiding	4	9.1	9.1
Compromising	8	18.2	27.3
Meeting	32	72.7	100.0
Total	44	100.0	

Data Source: Researcher field Survey, 2020

The above table of analysis indicated that majority said Meeting 72.7%, Compromising 18.2%, and Avoiding 9.1%

4.4. Differences between line managers and specialists with respect to age, education and attitude

Table 4.4. Differences between line managers and specialists with respect to age, education and attitude

Responses	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Low	3	6.8	6.8
Very low	5	11.4	18.2
Medium	10	22.7	40.9
High	26	59.1	100.0
Total	44	100.0	

Data Source: Researcher field Survey, 2020

Table analysis shown above indicated that Managers and specialist views were as follows high 59.15%, medium 22.7%, very low 11.4% and low 6.8% this indicates that there were differences between line managers and specialists with respect to age, education and attitude

4.5. Negative Effect of Conflict in an institution

Table 4.5. Negative Effect of Conflict in an institution

Responses	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Lack of inessential information	6	13.6	13.6
Reduced moral of work	8	18.2	31.8
High turn over	9	20.5	52.3
Downfall of the team work	10	22.7	75.0
Poor productivity	11	25.0	100.0
Total	44	100.0	

Data Source: Researcher field Survey, 2020

Table above also presents responses on negative effects of destructive conflict on employee productivity. Accordingly, 55% of response suggests destructive conflicts hurt group cohesion, 63% say it promotes interpersonal hostilities, 68% say it diverts energies, 59% states that it creates bad feelings, 67% of respondents suggest high labour turnover, and 51% chose costly litigations as the negative effects of destructive conflicts. On the ability of destructive conflicts to cause death, 49% said it can kill emotionally and spiritually whereas 53% said it can kill physically. Thus the respondents agree that apart from killing an individual emotionally and spiritually, destructive conflicts hurt group cohesion, promote interpersonal hostilities, divert energies, create bad feelings, lead to high labour turnover, costly litigations and it can even kill physically.

4.6. Conflict management should reduce conflict in the institution

4.6. Conflict management should reduce conflict in the institution

Responses	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Conciliation	2	4.5	4.5
Clear vision and mission of institution	3	6.8	11.4
Team work	5	11.4	22.7
Clear organization structure	6	13.6	36.4
Accountability	8	18.2	54.5
Clear rules and regulation	10	22.7	77.3
Regular meeting	10	22.7	100.0
Total	44	100.0	

Data Source: Researcher field Survey, 2020

Table of analysis above showed that Conflict management should be taken in order to reduce conflict in the institution conciliation 4.5% ,clear vision and mission of institution 6.8%, team work 11.4%, clear organization structure 13.6%, accountability18.2% ,clear rules and regulation 22.7% and regular meeting 22.7%.In this research question, the techniques adopted by managers in solving organizational conflict are as presented in table no.6. above

4.7. Causes of conflict between top management and staff in institution

Table 7. Causes of conflict between top management and staff in institution

Responses	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Scarce resources	6	13.6	13.6
Attitude	8	18.2	31.8
Poor communication	14	31.8	63.6
Lack of team work	16	36.4	100.0
Total	44	100.0	

Data Source: Researcher field Survey, 2020

Table 4.7 shows that in both respondents awareness was low since the percentage of those who asserted that they knew the causes of conflict. Furthermore, there was no great difference between those who said 'yes' and those who said 'no' in both councils. Table 7.shows that 12.9% indicate that institution conflict is caused by poor communication in lack of team work 36.4% Poor communication 31.8% attitude 18.2% scarce resources 13.6%. However, respondents did not respond to the question in the questionnaires provided. Indicate that it is caused by organizational policies and individual goals respectively. Indicate management style and ineffective reward system respectively. Indicate "all of the above this implies that these are causes of institutional conflict.

4.8. Major Style Use to Solve Conflict Management in an institution

Table 8. Style Use to Solve Conflict Management in an institution

Responses	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Avoiding	4	9.1	9.1
Compromising	10	22.7	31.8
Meeting	30	68.2	100.0
Total	44	100.0	

Data Source: Researcher field Survey, 2020

The above table of analysis indicated that the Style uses to Solve work place Conflict in the institution are as follows Meeting 68.2% Compromising 22.7% Avoiding 9.1%

4.9. Strategies used most to solve conflict between management and staff

Table .9. Strategies used most to solve conflict between management and staff

Responses	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Competitive conflict style	5	11.4	11.4
Yielding	6	13.6	25.0
Avoidance	9	20.5	45.5
Compromising conflict style	24	54.5	100.0
Total	44	100.0	

Data Source: Researcher field Survey, 2020

Analysis in the above table 9 indicated, he/she can note that the percentage of those who did not respond to the question in the questionnaire in institution was greater than those who responded, that is of respondents. In institution, it is only compromising conflict style 54.5% Avoidance 20.5% Yielding 13.6% Competitive conflict style 11.4% generally; the table shows that conflict resolution mechanisms existed in the two institutions. Furthermore, the researcher asked the respondents who said 'yes' to mention the mechanisms that were available in their respective institution

4.10. Conflict is inherently bad; it must be avoided and eliminated

Table. 10. Conflict is inherently bad; it must be avoided and eliminated

Responses	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Some time	10	22.7	22.7
Should be avoided	18	40.9	63.6
Always	16	36.4	100.0
Total	44	100.0	

Data Source: Researcher field Survey, 2020

Table 10 shows that inadequacy of funds was mentioned as the most itching problem with the frequency of 44 respondents (100%); followed by inherent disharmony between permanent public officials and councilors, with a frequency of 44 responses (100%); then Always 36.4.% Should be avoided 40.9% Sometime 22.7% and lastly, jealousy with responses. The total number of respondents was 44 100% respondents views that Conflict Is Inherently Bad

4.11. Conflict is important for better task accomplishment

Table 4.11. Conflict is important for better task accomplishment

Responses	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Some time	10	22.7	22.7
Always	14	31.8	54.5
No need of having	20	45.5	100.0
Total	44	100.0	

Data Source: Researcher field Survey, 2020

With being able to see results obviously, reveals that majority of respondents identified inadequate supervision and coaching, employee involvement in decision-making, less organizational bureaucracy, too much work, insufficient rewards and chances to advance, a greater sense of purpose and clear goals

4.12. Conflicts hamper affective interpersonal and group relationships

Table. 4.12. Conflicts hamper affective interpersonal and group relationships

Responses	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
No	8	18.2	18.2
Yes	36	81.8	100.0
Total	44	100.0	

Data Source: Researcher field Survey, 2020

Finally, respondents were asked to assess whether destructive conflicts affect productivity. Figure 5 below illustrates their responses. Whereas 18.2% of respondents suggest that destructive conflict does not affect productivity and 81.8% of respondents suggested destructive conflicts affect management activities.

4.13. Effective conflict management enhances managerial performance

Table.4.13. Effective conflict management enhances managerial performance

Responses	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
No	8	18.2	18.2
Yes	36	81.8	100.0
Total	44	100.0	

Data Source: Researcher field Survey, 2020

Above indicates that majority of respondents (81.8%) have ever experienced destructive conflict(s) in their institution while 18.2% have not experienced such conflict(s) in their institution however, effective conflict management enhances efficient managerial performance

4. Managerial Performance

4.1. Institution Perform Well

Table 4.1: Institution Perform Well

Responses	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
No	16	36.4	36.4
Yes	28	63.6	100.0
Total	44	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2020

The above table of analysis indicated that institution performing well as said by participant 63.6% Yes and others participant said No 36.4%

4.2. The financial results of the institution are declared for every

Table 4.2. The financial results of the institution are declared for every

Financial result	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Quarter	6	13.6	13.6
Half yearly	12	27.3	40.9
Yearly	26	59.1	100.0
Total	44	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2020

Result of analysis from SPSS show that the financial results of the institution are declared for every Quarterly (13.6%), Half yearly (27.3%), Yearly (59.1%)

4.3. Institution inform its audit committee

Table .4.3. Institution inform its audit committee

Responses	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Never Audit	2	4.5	4.5
Regularly Audit	12	27.3	31.8
Occasionally Audit	14	31.8	63.6
Irregularly Audit	16	36.4	100.0
Total	44	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2020

The table of analysis indicated the respondents views irregularly audit 36.4% occasionally audit 31.8% regularly audit 27.3% never Audit 4.5% institution inform its audit committee as and when funds are raised

4.4. Institutions funds, audited by its audit committee for accountability

Table 4.4. Institutions funds, audited by its audit committee for accountability

Views	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
No	18	40.9	40.9
Yes	26	59.1	100.0
Total	44	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2020

From table above 40.9% of the respondents say workplace conflicts have considerable impact on their productivity, while 59.1% disagree to it. This means that majority of the respondents agree that conflict in the workplace has considerable impact on the productivity of the institution and its employees

4.5. Summary Statement of all its transactions with related Parties, Periodically

Table 4.5. Summary Statement of all its transactions with related Parties, Periodically

Responses	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
No	16	36.4	36.4
Yes	28	63.6	100.0
Total	44	100.0	

Source: Field Survey 2020

Table of analysis showed that 63.6% participants said yes they submit a Summary Statement of all its transactions with related Parties, Periodically and 36.4% of respondents said no the institution does not submit a Summary Statement of all its transactions with related Parties, Periodically

4.6. Frauds during the Previous accounting Period

Table 4.6. Frauds during the Previous accounting Period

Responses	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
No	16	36.4	36.4
Yes	28	63.6	100.0
Total	44	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2020

The result of analysis indicated that yes 63.6% there any frauds taken place in the institution during the previous accounting period and 36.45% said no frauds during the Previous accounting Period management employees

4.7. Rate of Managerial Performance

Table 4.7. Rate of Managerial Performance

Responses	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
High	6	13.6	13.6
Low	8	18.2	31.8
Very high	10	22.7	54.5
Moderate	20	45.5	100.0
Total	44	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2020

Field Survey 2016 Accordingly, 56% selected lack of resources, 81% criticisms and gossip, 87% accusation, 69% unfair provision of different kinds of benefits (training opportunities), 75% chose pay cut without their consent, 84% said when individuals consistently fail to admit their weakness; lie, rationalize and deny; or apologize instead of changing behavior,

with 71% going in for individuals blaming others instead of “owning” their part of the problem or when they are defensive instead of being open to feedback. They thus agreed that the causes of destructive conflicts in their organization are lack of resources; criticisms and gossip; accusation; unfair provision of different kinds of benefits training opportunities pay cut without consent; individuals consistently failing to admit their weakness; lie, rationalize and deny; apologize instead of changing behavior

4.4. Rate the satisfaction at work place

Table. 4.8. Rate the satisfaction at work place

Responses	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Very high	4	9.1	9.1
Low	5	11.4	20.5
Very low	9	20.5	40.9
High	12	27.3	68.2
Moderate	14	31.8	100.0
Total	44	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2020

Rate the satisfaction at your work place very high 9.1%, low 11.45, very low 20.5%, high 27.3% and those who said they are moderate the satisfaction at work place 31.8%

4.9. Job Satisfaction helping to improve Managerial Performance

Table.4.9. Job Satisfaction helping to improve Managerial Performance

Responses	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
No	12	27.3	27.3
Yes	32	72.7	100.0
Total	44	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2020

Table of analysis above showed that Job Satisfaction helping to improve Managerial Performance and all managers should be focused on improving their employees' strengths through coaching. Unfortunately, almost half of managers spend less than said no an s 27.3% of their time coaching their team. It's no surprise, then, that only 72.7% of employees feel that their managers hold effective discussions about performance. Recognizing employees, especially by calling out accomplishments and helping employees get ahead in their careers. Inspiring employees to follow by showing them those leaders are competent, honest and reliable.

4.10. Effort being done to attain sustainable productivity in institution

Table 4.10. Effort being done to attain sustainable productivity in institution

Responses	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
No	14	31.8	31.8
Yes	30	68.2	100.0
Total	44	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2020

The respondent's opinion on effort being done to attain sustainable productivity in institution 68.2% said yes while 31.8% said no there was lack of effort being done to attain sustainable productivity in institution

4.11. Absenteeism at work place

Table. 4.11. Absenteeism at work place

Responses	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
No	12	27.3	27.3
Yes	32	72.7	100.0
Total	44	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2020

Analysis and discussion of data in analyzing the data, the information gathered from the table and figure above buttressed the point that Management are solely responsible for managing conflict at institution 72.7% yes and 27.3% participant said no absenteeism at work place does improve conflict management

4.12. Influence of absenteeism on managerial performance

Table 4.12. Influence of absenteeism on managerial performance

Responses	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
No	16	36.4	36.4
Yes	28	63.6	100.0
Total	44	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2020

From the above table 4.12 and figure 4.12 shows the impact of conflict among employees. All the 28 respondent representing 63.6% said influence of absenteeism on managerial performance affects them psychologically, and all the 20 respondents representing 36.4% said influence of absenteeism on managerial performance as well 36.4%

4.13. Relationship between employee behavior and managerial performance

Table. 4.13. Relationship between employee behavior and managerial performance

Responses	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
excellence	6	13.6	13.6
Very Good	8	18.2	31.8
Moderate	12	27.3	59.1
Good	18	40.9	100.0
Total	44	100.0	

Source: Field Survey, 2020

The table above shows that managers at workplace the disruptive behaviors that mostly affect employees' productivity. 91% of respondents identified loss of commitment to work, 69% chose broken relationship among employees; 81% of respondents consider work instability & insecurity, while 76% considered absenteeism as comprising those disruptive behaviors that mostly affect productivity of employees. The respondents thus agree that loss of commitment to work, broken relationship among employees, work instability and insecurity, as well as absenteeism are disruptive behaviors that mostly affect employees' productivity. Poor superior-subordinate relationship manifests in insensitivity to employees' plights, intimidation, with holding of promotion, communication gap and query. This causes conflict between superiors and subordinates

4.3. Interview analysis and information from secondary data

According to the documents and the interview conducted from managers, conflict arise in the institution because of the benefits and salary not being fairly paid, employees not obeying the

collective agreement or procedures of the institution. Also there are conflicts occurring between different levels of managements. Specially, between middle level managers with top level managers. Between the managers the main cause is as different managers have different types of personality to solve conflict.

There are different ways or methods and techniques use to solve conflict between the management and employees. They are consensus that is a method of problem solving in which the conflicting parties meet together to find the best solutions rather than to achieve a victory over each other. Collective agreement is which the labour union and the institution of a case study management prepared a procedure to work for the employee of the Ministry of Finance. But before ninety days before it must be reported to the management committee. And the last one is separation that is a form of compromise in which opposing parties are kept apart until they agree to a solution. Participants' understanding of conflict management the study sought to explore how well participants understood conflict management and managerial performance. The majority of the participants had an understanding of what conflict was. Frequency of conflict occurrence in the workplace At times, the experience of conflict by employees in an institution occurs quite often, often or rarely. The study sought to explore the frequency in which conflicts occur at institution. One of the employees lamented that the conflicts occur on a daily basis. Causes of conflicts amongst peer co-workers Failure to submit reports on time really cause conflict among peer co-workers in this institution. Participant also agreed with the above statement and mentioned the following you see according to me, I can say failure to submit the reports on time brings conflict as we work with deadlines in this institution and donors need the monthly reports on time. For me lack of time management, which leads to not submitting reports on time, thus not meeting the deadlines put up by the institution causes conflict. The study findings established that limited resources such as money, time and equipment are often scarce. Competition among people or departments for limited resources was a cause for conflict. It was established that when a group of employees have access to such resources while others do not, conflict may arise among peer co-workers. Important resources are often limited in the institution and were one cause of conflict.

Lack of clarity on roles and responsibilities participants mentioned that lack of clear roles and responsibilities of peer co-workers in the organization caused conflict between them. Lack of clear roles of every co-worker creates conflict, I want to know what I am supposed to do but without interfering with someone else's work. According to labour management agreement (collective agreement), management of the institutional takes various actions and measures to prevent and avoid the conflict generating factors. The degree of intensity of measures taken various, depending on the repetitiveness of the Occurrence of the action. Whenever conflict arises, conflict resolutions committee would be established.

Some of the committee includes: (i) Representative of the Human Resource Management, (ii) Representative of general Management and administration, (iii) Representative of chairman, and (iv) Representative of the labour union. The institution has obtained positive implications out of conflict by (i) Motivating the employees by giving rewards, (ii) Uniting the employees by forming annual reunions, (iii) It has helped to have a hard working employee, & (iv) Helping for innovating new working ideas.

5. Findings

The study has many findings; First, Gender of Respondents has an important component in determining the behavior or reaction of respondents towards conflicts in an organization. It is therefore significant to examine genders a category in this study. The data below show the Gender of the Respondents. Out of the 44 employees, 68.2% were male while the remaining 31.8% were female. There is gender balance among employees in the institution. The policy of gender equity has been upheld in the institution, it can be revealed that male staff responded to the various questions probably because of the nature of conflict management in the office. This is closely followed by female respectively; these sections have also encountered conflict in their various departments. Second, Discursion of age group of Respondents on the basis of age as shown in table 4.2, all respondents were above 35 years with over 60% of them aging above 50 years. Although, age may not always reflect knowledge, the caliber of respondents was observed to have adequately gathered so much knowledge and experience over their life time. This indicates that majority of the respondents are not on retirement age that shows the institution have strong men and women to work in the institution for a longer period of time. However, the Ministry has to employ more youth into the system to replace the retired staff in the near future. Third, Education levels vary substantially among people in a workplace. A higher level of education can be expected to increase in organization, as educated people are more likely tube engaged in various sections in the institution. In this study the educational levels of the respondents is significant because it is likely to impact on how conflict can be resolved when it happened in the workplace. The figure below shows the Educational Background of the Respondents. Educational qualification of the participants the study findings revealed that 36.4% of the participants were Undergraduate Degree holders as their highest educational qualification and Diploma holders with 34.1% Masters" Degree 18.2%, Certificate 11.4% were holders of undergraduate degrees were majority. It can be deduced from the study that employees were educated hence were in a position to understand the role of interpersonal communication in managing peer co-worker conflict. It is evident that, education level has an influence on the job satisfaction and employee performance. When employee has improved their education levels they become more aware of the job responsibilities as well as, their rights at work. Respondent insists that, conflict can occur to higher educated employees in their institutional because; they know and understand their rights when management misuses their power. The findings concur with that who argues that, the worker who had high education level are stronger in fighting their rights compared to those who had moderate or low level of education. They conclude that education in the institutional has influence on conflict management occurrences on managerial Performance. Four, Marital Status of Employees is another bio data that was asserted to be influencing dysfunctional conflict at the workplace. The results of employees' rating are indicated in table, Majority Married 34 (77.3%) of the respondents Marital Status to fill vacant positions in the institution. Howe Marital Status, this observation is contrary to a study that indicates that the most Marital Status. Other Single 13.6% and divorced 9.1% respondents respectively. This implies that the institution has more married employees than unmarried one. When the corporation faces dysfunctional conflict it means that, married couples were more engaged in the dysfunctional conflict. This is likely to bring marital conflict into workplace and lastly affect the performance of the work. Indicates in his findings that, marital status, demographic groups differ among married and unmarried. He argued that if the conflict happened at the institution may be influenced mostly by married employees. Five, Job Title of respondents depicts that constituted the largest number of respondents that is 24 Accountants (54.5%) of the respondents. Administrators were 10 (22.7%), and 13.6% officers were 9.1%. head of Department. The findings concluded that, Job title of respondents in institution has significance influence on conflict if those employees

not satisfied with their job. The studies concluded that occupation of core function has positive impact on conflict management and managerial performance. Six, working experience of employees, Work output and productivity largely depends on appropriate experience. It was therefore necessary to establish the experience of the employees. Table of analysis indicate their responses. The period of years a person has been in the ministry may determine the number of time she/she has encounter conflict in the workplace and have idea of what causes the conflict and the kind of effects it sometimes have on the productivity of the employees. The table below is the distribution of data on the duration of respondents. Duration of Respondents Working In the Ministry, 36.4% of the employees had a working experience of less than five year, another 31.8% had working experience of between 5 and 10 years, 27.3% had worked for between 11 and 16 years while 4.5% had a working experience of over 17 years, the majority were middle staff members of institution. Six, The causes of conflict in an institution could be grouped into three broad areas namely intra-personal, interpersonal and inter-group. Seven, under the intra-personal conflict, conflicts emerged when a staff member was faced with the challenge of making a choice among a set of options that had good or bad outcomes. Issues related to unclear roles related to their job also created intra-personal conflicts. Eight, The promoters of inter-personal conflict in Ministry of Finance and planning are: competing for limited resources, recognition, power struggle, differences in behavior, and differences in perception among individual staff. Nine, Issues such as limited resources, deficiencies in information flow, conflicting interest, overlapping tasks, time pressure and collective decision making led to inter-group conflict in Ministry of Finance. Ten, The positive effects of conflict on management performance in Ministry of Finance and planning include encouragement of positive change and innovation in the polytechnic as well as regularity and punctuality of staff attendance to work. Eleven, Staff perceived apathy, low commitment level, low job satisfaction, loss of interest and poor performance of work as negative effects of conflict on staff performance. Additionally, Ministry encounters conflicts in relation to motivational issues such as allowances, staff development staff accommodation and annual leave. These conflict contexts cut across intrapersonal; interpersonal and intergroup conflict perspectives. Moreover, Ministry of Finance and Planning is aware of and uses the various primary conflict management approaches, which include competition, collaboration, avoidance, accommodation and compromise. Finally, In addition to the use of primary conflict management approaches in handling conflict among staff at the Ministry management makes use of disciplinary committee, meetings to resolve conflicts to build bridges, guidance and counseling units, organizing seminars and enforcement of rules and regulation of the institutions as well as inter-departmental games as other approaches of handling conflict among staff.

6. Conclusions

Conflict management (bargaining, compromise, and force) has improved significantly, as has employee morale. This suggests that dispute resolution techniques including negotiation, compromise, and coercion have a statistically significant impact on enhancing managerial performance morale in the Ministry. That is, Ministry has increased staff morale through controlling disputes. Based on the findings, a number of conclusions can be drawn. Conflict at all levels exists among staff and these are intra-personal, inter-personal and inter-group. The various causes of these levels of conflict have been established. Conflicts among staff impact positively and negatively on managerial performance as well as the overall objective of the Ministry of Finance. Staffs employ the primary conflict management approach in handling conflict among them. However, there are significant differences in the use of those approaches by individuals and among the various groups of staff at the Ministry of Finance. Negotiation strategy

enables the organizations to maintain a strategic distance from clashes and enhance relations among the workers. Having the ability to mastermind sufficiently has any kind of effect the associations achieve understandings, accomplish goals, coexist better with its workforce, and at last be increasingly profitable and fruitful at work. Compromise strategy helps the management to determine debate rapidly, which is imperative when an extended difference could conceivably wreck a period touchy errand or when there is the need to keep a stewing struggle from rising. A workplace culture built on tolerance is promoted by institutions that employ compromise to resolve disagreements. Individuals and management must thus use the most effective conflict management style to reduce the dysfunctional aspects of conflict and enhance the functional aspects for the growth and development of both parties involved as well as the company as a whole.

6.1. Implications

The middle and junior staffs, as well as financial administration, are the areas of institution administration most influenced by work place conflict, according to this study. As a result, administration management must be cautious in their financial interactions with all stakeholders, including accountants, administrators, and other employees. They should also prioritize the interests of employees in all policies, programs, rules, and laws that are implemented, since stakeholders who are comfortable with the management style will have less conflict in the system. Because we stated at the outset that conflicts are unavoidable in all human relationships, they must inevitably emerge in both the public and private sectors. As a result, when disputes do develop, administrators should be able to address them using conflict resolution techniques that produce positive rather than negative consequences. Furthermore, this thesis proposes the establishment of a case study conflict management or resolution to accomplish progressive elevation of society's quality and standard via the employment of confrontational, conversation, committee, and compromise conflict resolution techniques. As a result, the confrontational method will aid management in maintaining their ground, confronting difficulties head-on, and instilling confidence in the workplace. Finally, another technique that the Ministry's administration might use to handle conflict is conversation. It will allow all parties involved contributing to the resolution of the dispute, and when this is done well, such problems are less likely to resurface. Because managers/Directors who combine both strategies would assign tasks to others, providing them with adequate time to attend to other administrative chores but must continuously monitor the work, this style is better done if abridged with the committee setup approach.

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